

The impact of TV advertisement on the Life style of Pakistani youth (Gujarat-Pakistan, March-2014)

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to acquire the role of the TV advertisement in changing the life style of Pakistani youth in accordance with their attitude, habit, moral values and taste. It was a community-based analytical study, which prevailed from January 2014 to March 2014. A group of 200 respondents took part in the study out of which 92 were female, 108 were male, and data was collected from University of Gujrat. In results, females and males both point out that the advertisement has an impact on changing the lifestyle of youth in accordance with their habits, attitude, taste and moral values.

Keywords: *impact, lifestyle, Youth, Advertisement.*

Introduction

Television is a popular leisure time activity and it is popular all most in every part of the world. It promotes sedentary lifestyle by contravention on time available for physical activity. The effect of television is great due to audio and visual effect. This feature of TV is world widely acknowledged and used as effective tool for advertisement. First television advertisement was made in United States on July 1, 1941. First TV advertisement made in Asia was on August 28, 1953 on Nippon Television in TOKYO.

In past TV commercial was totally different from that of today. In those days the black and white advertisement was used, they had white middle class actors and they were much longer than today's advertisement. Nowadays, TV medium is totally different and it consists of familiar technical techniques of print media. Advertisement in 1970 was totally different from the past as a result of information technology and TV image got better too. Viewers were also changing, becoming more television literate and visually predisposed demanding higher production value. Television network was established in the late 1940 and early 1950.

Till 1990 TV advertisement was affordable only by large companies but after arrival of desktop video, it allowed many small and local businesses to produce television ads. During the past few years there has been a great increase in advertisement expenses all over the world. Therefore it is important to evaluate the performance of advertisement to reach the organization objectives.

Companies invest large amounts of their earnings in advertisement in different media such as television radio magazine etc. the purpose of these advertisements is to create a favorable image in the mind of consumer and position their product above those of their rivals and influence the customer behavior through TV advertisement. TV advertisement is an important source of advertisement for new product than any other media.

Advertising as a major social event expresses a vital change in beliefs, behavior, value and patterns of buying of the people which influence the lifestyles of people (Polly and Mittal, 1993). Hoo and Munusamy (2007) cited that attitude toward advertising is a core concept and basically is one of

the determinants of attitude towards any particular advertisement (Lutz, 1985). People are attracted and motivated through TV ads as like what to wear, what to eat etc. They often just buy things because their peers buy those things and fascinate to buy along and it is all due to TV advertisement.

In this research paper, 'The impact of TV advertisement on lifestyle of Pakistani youth' we are going to find the impact of TV advertisement on life style of youth in relation to the combination of some factors (variables) such as habits, attitude, taste and moral values. Danial Czitrom and David Marc (1985) provide a sketch to the popularity of lifestyle in 1960 when several lifestyles became known to individuals and groups including communal, gay, youth and student lifestyle, all forming alternative lifestyles.

Aim of the study

The purpose of this study is to determine the role of TV advertisement in the life style of Pakistan youth with the help of habits, attitude, taste, moral standard parameters and to determine in which extent advertisement is used in changing life style and its impact on society. It will be a community based study in Pakistan. People today watch TV which provides them every kind of information and they take affect from it. We will be searching that to what extent the TV advertisement is effective and what impact it has on the life style of youth. We will be conducting this research just on the youth that what kind of role TV advertisement plays in their life. For this we will conduct a simple non random convenient sampling method, in University of Gujrat and drive our results.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study is to access to the role of TV advertisement in changing the lifestyle of Pakistani youth and also measure that to which extent is advertisement useful in doing so plus its impact on the society. This would be a replicate study, the original research was conducted in different universities of Islamabad (Pakistan) during a time period of March to June 2001. We are going to conduct the research in Gujrat (Pakistan) by taking surveys from the students of University of Gujrat. The original study took a time period of 4 months and we ought to conduct it within a period of 3 months from January 2014 to March 2014.

For this purpose a sample of 200 students will be taken on basis of convenient sampling method. After that we will use SPSS 16 to run t-test, regression and correlation technique and a descriptive analysis. To test hypothesis we will use the Regression technique. Our hypothesis will be that either there will be an association between advertisement and changing lifestyle of Pakistani youth or vice versa on the basis of attributes taken.

Research Question

Is there an association or impact of TV advertisement on the changing lifestyle of youth or not?

Significance/rationale of the study

The results would contribute that either TV advertisement has a positive or a negative impact on the changing of the lifestyle of youth via the impact it plays on the four variables taste, attitude, habit and moral values.

Companies could use this information to mould them and use an effective way of making TV advertisements, accordingly, to attract youth more but in a manner that the lifestyle of youth changes in a positive way. In most of the research papers it is concluded that there is strong association between advertisement and the changing life style of youth.

Theoretical contribution

The theoretical contribution of this study will provide valuable information about the effects of TV advertisement on the lifestyle of youth via four different variables. The theoretical framework and the result of this study will provide initial two contributions. It will provide a theoretical understanding and experimental testing of the mechanisms by which the TV advertisement affects the lives of youth, including the study of the potential effects of differential factors like Taste, Habit, Moral values and Attitude that contribute towards changing of the lifestyle.

Literature review

Shanthy A. Bowman conducted a research from (1994-1996) for the purpose of examining the association among eating practices, overweight and health status & television viewing in United States. The study used a sample of adults above 29 (male female) years age and data were collected through an interviewer using multi pass technique and then it was processed through multiple regressions. The results showed that adults who watch television more than 2 hours consume more energy-rich snacks type food, grain mixture like pizza and regular soft drinks as compare to adults who watch less than one hour.

DJBA conducted the research from (1998 -1999), does television viewing predict intake five year later in high school adults. Television viewing especially during high school may have long term effects on eating choices and contributes poor eating habits in young adulthood. He collected data from 564 students of middle school randomly and a questionnaire was used to collect the data which included television viewing time and food frequency. He used multivariate regression model to run a separate analysis

for younger and older students and found that television viewing during adolescence especially viewing during high school year predicts future eating habits.

“Advertisement plays an important role nowadays in persuading consumers to purchase product and services but unfortunately consideration to assessment of advertisement effectiveness is less and only some organizations and industries evaluate the effectiveness of their advertisement (McCarthy 2000)”.

Mohammad Esmaeil Ansari (November 2011) conducted a research on investigation of TV advertisement effect on consumers purchasing and their satisfaction. He used AIDA model as a hierarchy of effective model in advertising for investigation the effects. He developed 5 hypotheses. The objective of this research was to clarify the effects of TV advertisement on consumer attention to advertisement interest for purchasing desire and action for purchasing and eventually customer’s satisfaction. It was a descriptive research and cross sectional sampling of population was done in it. And a questionnaire was used the first part of which consisted of demographical questions and second part was designed to test hypotheses and contained 4 questions for each hypotheses. Correlation and regression were used and after that all hypotheses were significant and it concussed that TV advertisement have positive effect on consumers’ attention regarding interest for purchasing, advertisement & desire for buying-action of Purchasing and customers' satisfactions.

“Appearance of objects visually first moves to neural within diverse brain areas and helps the product acknowledgment and education. By using different methods, we can increase the quality of visuals used in ads and packaging (Palmeri, *at al* 2002). Relationship between colors and buying behavior is very profound. The sample of 200 people ranging from 15 to 55 years of age was collected. Both male & female respondents were included in the snowball sample Collection of primary data for this research paper through questionnaire and the questionnaires. Among all respondents 40.9% were males and 59.06% were females. Regression analysis was used for analyzing the data which showed that color and packaging have positive affect in advertisement for buying behavior, have strong positive impacts on consumer buying behavior.

Attitude plays a central role within most behaviors model. According to Schiffmann and Kanuk (2004), “attitudes are predispositions learned by an individual which allow him /her to behave in a consistently favorable or unfavorable way with respect to an object”.

During the past few years there has been tremendous increase in advertisement expenses in entire world. So it is important to investigate and to evaluate the performance of advertisement to reach organizations objectives (Huang, 2006; Van Raaij, 1998)”. Habibollah Danaei conducted a research on investigating the effect of advertisement on consumer behavior in Iran. For this purpose they used the most popular models called AIDA. The survey selected a sample of 300 regular customers and distributed a standard questionnaire among them. All questions of the survey were designed in Likert Scale verified and results showed a

positive impact of four factors attention, interest, desire and action on consumer's behavior using Spearman correlation ratio. TV attraction played the most important role on getting consumers' attention.

"Major aspect of life of females is affected by watching cable television, Zia (2007)". He searched the relationship between level of education of females and watching time of cable television. For this purpose, he used convenient sampling method in Swat and structured questionnaire were used. Data was analyzed in SPSS 16 by contingency table. And chi square was used. For testing significance in the population, the chi square test was used. 35% of educated females were viewers of cable television for the knowledge aspect, 65% percent of respondent have been watching cable television for entertainment.

Raluca BĂBUȚ (February 2012) conducted a study on the Roman consumer's attitude towards TV commercial. He used 550 people, 18 year old, how watched TV and collected data by means of face to face interview. He used equate sampling method according to age and sex. Then he used correlation and the results showed that majority of population show favorable attitude to advertisement.

"Petrovici and Marinov (2007)" said that Core reasons for the change in the lifestyle and buying pattern of a person are the economic transformation and certain market chances". It was conducted to evaluate the General Attitude towards Advertising Cultural Influence in Pakistan. For this purpose a sample of 250 people was taken from Islamabad and questionnaires were distributed to collect data from 250 respondents which were involved directly in purchasing. It included adults from all disciplines including house wives from within the vicinity of Islamabad/Rawalpindi and then Regression was used to check the results of product information social integration and hedonism over public general attitude towards advertisement. To study the attitude of consumers towards advertising a one-way analysis of variance ANOVA was used and results showed that culture has a strong influence as a moderator over hedonism and social integration impact on general attitude towards advertising.

A Study done by (Shabbir, 2008) shows that Pakistani children are very much aware about TV commercial's features like annoyingness, taste, truthfulness and influencing characteristics of the ads. A research was conducted by the students of Pakistan for this purpose. They used a convenient sampling method in Islamabad and questionnaires were designed to take the data. It was community base sampling and the results were analyzed in SPSS 16 by chi-square the research was conducted from June to march 2011. The questionnaire was designed to know the point of view of youth regarding the impact of

advertisement in changing the life style. First part of questionnaire contained information regarding demographics. Second part had the series of close-ended indirect questions which were based on lifestyle variables like believes, Norm, Cultural value, family bonding and tendency to copy Ads. The results showed that TV advertisement in general and those involving same celebrities have immense and lasting effect on religious value, family bonding & lifestyle of youth and decision making criteria of them for buying various items.

Parents are usually the most credible information source about advertisements for children (Fan and Li, 2009.) Advertisements are an important information source for new products and services. Various factors such as social class, economic, age, presentation of message, structure of family and relationships governing the time watching television effect on child's perception of TV advertisements. The research was conducted to find TV advertisement messages among the elementary students of Isfahan city. For this purpose sample of 385 students was obtained by means of cluster random sampling method. Survey of 385 elementary students of ages 7 to 11 was conducted in Isfahan City using a structured questionnaire. Then it was processed in SPSS 16, the results showed that children's' perception about TV ads intents are influenced by family social class. Also, there was a significant positive relationship between children's social class and their perception about why some TV ads are attractive.

Methodology

Data collection

Primary data has been used in this paper. A survey is conducted regarding TV advertisement impact on lifestyle of youth. The respondents of this study are students of UOG within the age group of 18 years to 25 years or above from Gujrat city in Pakistan.

Sample size

The sample size for this study is of 200 respondents.

Time period: The time period to complete our research paper took almost 2 months.

Instrument

A simple non random sampling technique is used and a questionnaire is distributed to the respondents for collection of the data. The instrument contains a total of 22 questions of which 1 is related to gender(nominal), 1 is related to age(ratio), 4 questions(interval) are related to our each variable i.e. TV advertisement, taste, moral standards, habits and attitude respectively.

Theoretical Framework:

Independent Variables

Taste: Taste is an individual's personal and cultural patterns of choice and preference.

Attitude: Attitude is a favor or disfavor toward a person, place, thing, or event (the attitude object).

Moral values: Morality is the differentiation of intentions, decisions, and actions between those that are "good" (or right) and those that are "bad" (or wrong).

Habit: A habit is a routine of behavior that is repeated regularly and tends to occur subconsciously.

Data analysis method

Data is analyzed using a detailed descriptive analysis, regression and correlation technique and t-test.

To test Hypothesis we are using the Regression technique.

In addition, our hypothesis is:

Ho: No association between advertisement and in changing life style of youth

H1: An association exists between advertisements an in changing life style of youth.

Results & Analysis

Table 1 shows Reliability Analysis:

Reliability Test is applied to see whether the data is internally consistent or not. Its minimum value should be at least 0.4 for the data to be valid and accurate for further testing. The reliability test gives a value of 0.656 which means the data is 65.6% internally consistent and that the tests can be applied on it for further verifications.

Table 2 shows Descriptive Analysis:

Gender is a nominal scale question. Its measure of central tendency is on mode, the most repeated value. The results interpret that the most repeated value is representing males to be in greater ratio than females.

Age is a ratio scale question. Its measure of central tendency is on mean, the average results. The results interpret that average population lies between 20-24 years of age.

The dependent and independent variables are based on interval scale questions. Its measure of central tendency is on mean, the average results.

Dependent variable is TV advertisement and independent variables are attitude, habit, moral values and taste. Their results predict that average results been chosen are slightly deviating above the 3rd option.

Table 3 shows T-TEST:

The T-test interprets the significance level of all the variables.

T-test being applied on dependent variable and independent variables gave a 0.00% level of significance which is less than 0.05% declaring the results to be 100% significant.

Table 4 shows Correlation Test:

Correlation is the relationship between two or more than two variables. But it is not known which variable is dependent and which are independent.

There are five variables present which include TV advertisement, Attitude, Habit, Moral values and Taste.

TV advertisement shows positive or direct relation with Attitude and Habit. 1% change in Attitude and Habit brings 0.58% and 0.842% change in TV advertisement in same direction respectively.

TV advertisement shows negative or indirect relation with Moral values and Taste. 1% change in Moral values and Taste brings 0.828% and 0.424% change in TV advertisement but in opposite direction respectively.

Attitude shows positive or direct relation with Habit. 1% change Habit brings 0.553% change in Attitude in same direction.

Attitude shows negative or indirect relation with Moral Values and Taste. 1% change in Moral Values and Taste brings 0.189% and 0.027% change in Attitude but in opposite direction respectively.

Habit shows negative or indirect relation with Moral Values and Taste. 1% change in Moral Values and Taste brings 0.756% and 0.106% change in Habit but in opposite direction respectively.

Moral Values show positive or direct relation with Taste only. 1% change in Taste brings 0.528% change in Moral Values in same direction.

P value is 0.000% which is less than 0.05% so all variables is significant.

Regression Test:

Regression is the relationship between two or more than two variables. It is clear in regression that which variable is dependent and which are independent.

There are five variables in which TV advertisement is the dependent variable whereas Attitude, Habit, Moral values and Taste are the independent variables.

Table 5.1:

The Model Summary R square interprets the overall fitness of the model. Higher the value more fit the model is. R square value is 0.883 which shows that our model is fit.

The significance level of all the variables is 0.000% except Taste. Taste shows a significant level of 0.001%.

Table 5.2:

The regression equation for our model is:

$$Y = a + b(\text{Attitude}) + c(\text{Habit}) - d(\text{Moral Values}) - e(\text{Taste})$$

Where:

Y= TV advertisement, a= Constant, b=coefficient of Attitude, c=coefficient of Habit, d=coefficient of Moral Values, e= coefficient of Taste

Now applying the values of coefficients in equation:

TV advertisement
= 2.429 + 0.355Attitude
+ 0.118Habit – 0.205Moral Values
– 0.055Taste

Interpretation of Equation:

1% change in Taste brings 0.055% change in TV advertisement but in opposite direction.

1% change in Moral Values brings 0.205% change in TV advertisement but in opposite direction.

1% change in Habit brings 0.118% change in TV advertisement but in same direction.

1% change in Attitude brings 0.355% change in TV advertisement but in same direction.

ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS

H1: There is an association between advertisement and in changing life style of Pakistani youth.

Ho: There is no association between advertisement and in changing life style of Pakistani youth.

To test hypothesis we analyze the association of advertisement with life style variables through Regression technique. This concludes that all the values of p are less than 0.05% so Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Conclusion

We started with the aim to conceive the role of advertisement in changing the lifestyle of youth. Our findings provided some altruistic (beneficial) insights for future researchers and marketing managers.

We ended up with the findings on the bases of above-mentioned statistics. We can safely conclude that TV advertisement in general has immense and lasting effect on youths' lifestyle. Some of the effects are really damaging for our society, which are generally based on moral values and taste.

Future Research/Recommendations

This research has been limited to one city, one university and one country. Future researchers can explore on a broader level. They can change the number of cities. A different sector could be chosen and a different country could be chosen. We worked on a developing country's university. The culture, values and norms differ with almost every 100kms so a change in these could have lead to different results.

A developed country could be targeted and the variables on which we worked could be changed and worked upon. Different variables exist that can affect the lifestyle of youth. Our research is based upon four variables mainly. These could be changed or increased in number.

Our research focuses mainly on the youth! A different age group could be focused like children or middle aged people or older people. Apart from TV advertisement; different TV dramas, different TV programs or channels could be chosen on for a different research which would lead to a whole different scenario.

1. The field needs an ongoing research effort to monitor advertising and marketing practices aimed at children and youth.

An ongoing inventory of advertising methods will help the public health community and other child advocates stay current on the latest techniques being used to market to teenagers and children. The vast use of mobile and internet media has created a totally new world of advertising to children and teens, and academic research hasn't come close to keeping pace with all the changes. A broad guiding project would help inform "effects" research; ground policy debates in current practices; and bolster the efforts of pro-social marketers trying to reach young people with critical messages.

2. Researchers need to develop new methods to quantify young people's exposure to advertising.

Even basic research on the amount of advertising children and teenagers are exposed to is woefully out of date and incomplete. In fact, given the dramatic changes in advertising methods and platforms, there isn't even a reliable methodology for measuring young people's exposure to advertising and marketing messages. The blurring of the lines between advertising and "content" that is inherent in so many of the new techniques of marketing to children makes it difficult for researchers to distinguish the marketing messages and quantify children's exposure to them. Campaigns cross so many platforms—from product placement to online games and Facebook apps—that we need new methods for counting marketing messages and for comparatively assessing children's overall exposure to them (e.g., how much "weight" should be given to the frequent appearances of Starbucks drinks on *The Voice* or Coke on *American Idol*?).

3. Research is needed to help assess at what age (if ever) children can discern the marketing messages in new media, as well as how well they are able to understand and defend against the persuasive intent of these messages. At this point we lack even the most rudimentary research needed for policymakers to ascertain whether certain types of practices of marketing to children are fair, such as enlisting them as "viral" marketers, provoking to purchase products through incentives, opening them to placement of the product in famous shows of TV and enticing them to make their own ads and enter them in a contest. How does a child evaluate an invite from a friend asking him or her to visit a food company's website and play a branded advertisement game over there? How does children process the cues for brands in a mobile game? How does a teen assess a tweet from a celebrity inviting him or her to view a new YouTube video sponsored by a soda company?

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Appendix

Table 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha ^a	N of Items
.656	5

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

		What is your gender	Mark where your age falls in	TV advertisement	Attitude	Habit	Moral values	Taste
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.4600	2.0800	3.0812	3.0475	3.0712	3.0625	3.0750
Median		1.0000	2.0000	2.7500	3.2500	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000
Mode		1.00	2.00	2.50	3.50	4.00	5.00	4.00
Std. Deviation		.49965	.42956	.60356	.56510	1.38399	1.45380	1.38889
Variance		.250	.185	.364	.319	1.915	2.114	1.929
Minimum		1.00	1.00	2.25	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		2.00	3.00	4.25	4.25	5.00	5.00	5.00
Percentiles	25	1.0000	2.0000	2.5000	2.7500	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000
	50	1.0000	2.0000	2.7500	3.2500	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000
	75	2.0000	2.0000	3.5000	3.5000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000

Table 3

T-Test

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
TV advertisement	72.198	199	.000	3.08125	2.9971	3.1654
Attitude	76.266	199	.000	3.04750	2.9687	3.1263
Habit	31.383	199	.000	3.07125	2.8783	3.2642
Moral values	29.791	199	.000	3.06250	2.8598	3.2652
Taste	31.311	199	.000	3.07500	2.8813	3.2687

Table 4

Correlations

Correlations

		TV advertisement	Attitude	Habit	Moral values	Taste
TV advertisement	Pearson Correlation	1	.580**	.842**	-.828**	-.424**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.580**	1	.553**	-.189**	-.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.007	.705
	N	200	200	200	200	200
Habit	Pearson Correlation	.842**	.553**	1	-.756**	-.106
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.135
	N	200	200	200	200	200
Moral values	Pearson Correlation	-.828**	-.189**	-.756**	1	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.007	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200
Taste	Pearson Correlation	-.424**	-.027	-.106	.528**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.705	.135	.000	
	N	200	200	200	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5
Regression

Table 5.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.940 ^a	.883	.880	.20883

a. Predictors: (Constant), Taste, Attitude, Moral values, Habit

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.989	4	15.997	366.836	.000 ^a
	Residual	8.504	195	.044		
	Total	72.492	199			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Taste, Attitude, Moral values, Habit

Table 5.2 Coefficients

Model		Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.429	.103		23.545	.000
	Attitude	.355	.037	.333	9.482	.000
	Habit	.118	.027	.271	4.395	.000
	Moral values	-.205	.026	-.493	-8.010	.000
	Taste	-.055	.016	-.126	-3.416	.001

a. Dependent Variable: TV advertisement